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Useful Resources on Ageism, Older Persons and COVID-19

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The novel coronavirus is changing the way we live our lives. International organisations, governments, local authorities, civic society and each of us is making unprecedented efforts to stop the spreading of the disease. It is now more important than ever to protect older persons' rights now and refrain from ageism and ageist practice. We, the members of the EuroAgeism network, aim to raise awareness about older persons' rights and the outbreak of ageism during the pandemic. Below you can find links to our partner organisations' work on COVID-19:

[Age Platform Europe - COVID-19 webpage](#)

[European Centre for social welfare policy and research](#)

[WHO – Guidelines to avoid social stigma](#)

[UNECE - COVID-19 and older persons](#)

References and other resources:

International Long-Term Care Policy Network (ILPN) and the Care Policy and Evaluation Centre (CPEC) [website on long-term care during the COVID-19 outbreak](#)

British Society for Gerontology, [“Statement on COVID-19”](#)

International Federation on Ageing, [“Open letter to World Health Organization \(and to Member States\). WHO must prioritise the needs of older people in its response to the Covid-19 pandemic”](#)

Worldometer. [Age, Sex, Existing Conditions of COVID-19 Cases and Deaths.](#)

International Federation on Ageing, [“COVID-19 Resource Library”](#)

Age Platform, [“Coronavirus COVID-19”](#)

United Nations Population Fund, [“COVID-19: A Gender Lens”](#)

Age International, [“Covid-19 Crisis: Age International working to reach those most vulnerable”](#)

HelpAge International, [“HelpAge International initiatives on COVID-19”](#)

Independent Age statement, [“Joint statement on treatment rights of older people during pandemic”](#)

U.S. Department of Health & Human Services, [“The Office for Civil Rights of the U.S Department of Health and Human Services bulletin”](#)

Alzheimer’s Disease International, [“ADI offers advice and support during COVID-19”](#)

Health and Social Care Alliance Scotland, [“Policy briefing about the Scottish Parliament Coronavirus Bill”](#)

United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific, [“The Impact and Policy Responses for COVID-19 in Asia and the Pacific”](#)

Centre for Ageing Better UK, [“In light of the COVID-19 outbreak, articles that celebrate a cull’ of the elderly remind us to think more carefully about our attitudes towards ageing”](#)

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